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DIGITAL DISTRACTIONS AND THEIR EFFECT ON LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCRASTINATION

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INTRODUCTION:

ABSTRACT

Students are more vulnerable to distractions in the digital age, which might impede their academic progress, especially while learning a language. In this article, our primary goal is to investigate the persistently distracting issues that language study practices face, particularly concerning the main contribution of digital tools, social media, and constant online access, as these issues are allegedly encountered daily by our students in this Age of Distractions. Also, digital distractions like instant gratification, and the fear of missing out (FOMO), can cause many problems and this article discusses such kind of psychological factors of laziness. Furthermore, the article examines how the virtual environment influences learners' concentration, highlighting how these elements can cause faded attention and extended challenge avoidance. Ultimately, the study emphasizes the necessity of efficient time management plans and self-control exercises to lessen the negative impacts of digital distractions.

KEYWORDS: Academic procrastination, language learners, digital distractions, students, technology, social media, survey, receive notifications, results, productivity.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

PROCRASTINATION AND ITS TYPES

The pertinent literature lists various forms of procrastination because it is so prevalent in people's lives. Compulsive procrastination, which involves delaying decisions and tasks, and life routine procrastination, which refers to the inability to manage daily routine duties, are two examples of these behavior patterns. After these

two categories, the most common ones are academic procrastination, which occurs in academic settings when students, for various reasons, put off or dilatorily complete their academic tasks, and administrative and attendance tasks, and decisional procrastination, which occurs when choosing among the alternatives in complex and conflict situations.

ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION

Given how common academic procrastination is among students, many academics believe that this construct is relevant to other concepts. However, despite the fact that language acquisition necessitates completing several tasks, which may increase the likelihood of delaying activities, language learners' academic procrastination seems to be overlooked in the relevant literature. Despite this, it is easy to see that there is little research examining language learners' academic procrastination (Bekleyen, 2017). Bekleyen (2017) examined 313 first-year university freshmen majoring in English in one of these uncommon studies. Examined were the connections between students' self-reported motivation, gender, age, major satisfaction, and academic procrastination. Males reported procrastinating more than females, and the results showed a negative relationship between academic procrastination and motivation. (Mehmet Asmalı, Sanem Dilbaz Sayın, 2022)

VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT'S EFFECT ON CONCENTRATION

Since they grew up with technology, the majority of learners are familiar with its many functions. Both inside and outside the classroom, university students' learning is greatly enhanced by the use of this technology. But even with all of technology's advantages, these digital pursuits may also cause a lot of digital distractions. Internet browsing, movie viewing, texting, emailing, and social media browsing are examples of digital distractions. In addition to lowering learning and academic achievement generally, these digital distractions frequently lead to decreased focus and participation in language learning classes. (Wang et al.) Anxiety and sadness, motivating considerations, the need to be up to date the fear of losing out, emotional numbness and procrastination, and an excessive dependence on several sources can all lead to digital distraction. In a poll at a small institution, Tindell and Bohlander (2012) discovered that 92% of the students who took part said they sent text messages on their phones while in class. People find it challenging to focus and pay attention to tasks while they are using their smartphones for these off-task activities. Furthermore, the incessant information that smart gadgets provide us with – such as emails, social media news, Facebook updates, and notifications – takes up our attention and impairs our capacity for concentration and productivity (Leysens et al. 2016). According to

research by Seemiller (2017), using digital gadgets in class can lead to two possible issues. According to a study by Flanigan and Babchuk (2020), most teachers attempt to reduce digital distraction in their classes by emphasizing prevention; nevertheless, many also find it difficult to control the digital distraction that students engage in.

ONE REASON OF CHANGING PROFESSIONS OF YOUNG PEOPLE

These days, people look to others for validation and admiration in an indirect way. People who don't feel heard in real life often post things on social media because they know that people will read them and that their want for attention will be satisfied. The pleasant aspects of life are demonstrated by postings they publish about themselves. They often feel awkward and excluded when people read their posts about all the fascinating things they are doing. Therefore, people utilize additional social media apps to keep up with their friends; and interests, which exacerbates FOMO. Additionally, they experience low self-esteem as a result of the social comparisons they make on social networking sites. The idea of "friendship contingent self-esteem" further demonstrates how a person's sense of self is influenced by the opinions of others. A person's self-esteem is strongly impacted by the comments and likes they receive on their posts on social networking sites. (Garg, G. 2023) Both of them are common among young and some younger are fully addicted to this kind of self-assessment. Trying to achieve popularity via the Internet also affects aspiring young people so students who are learning some type of language or other thing, are being bloggers by leaving their professions.

CONS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON EDUCATION

Many university students no longer buy the required textbooks, and some have never been to a library. Students who are accustomed to browsing, surfing, and skimming online often read print materials in a similar way, with primary and secondary students going to Wikipedia first, followed by their Facebook network of "friends," their library, and possibly their school books. While using social media is not cheating in and of itself, teachers who want their students to learn how to find reliable sources and others frequently forbid using social media in assignments (Kishan, S. 2014).

Unless appropriately managed, developing technologies may be very distractive and may also impact badly on the learning tools utilized by students in a converged learning space, densely filled by apps of every variety (Liam Murray 2020). To deal with such distractions, students must first become alert to the distractive character of technology. Given the proliferation of mobile devices and apps, we need to become digitally literate in order to contribute to modern society.

METHODS:

This study employed three online surveys via a poll on the Telegram platform to collect data regarding the impact of smartphone notifications on students' concentration and language learning. The choice of Telegram as the medium for the survey was strategic, given its widespread use among students and its ability to facilitate quick and efficient data collection. The research's target demographic was sophomores of the English Philology Faculty at World State Language University who enrolled in language courses. Participants were gathered using a variety of methods, such as peer recommendations, social networking sites, and university groups on Telegram. The main reason for gathering information by Telegram poll is to access easily of participants. To encourage participation, a brief introduction was provided at the beginning of the survey, explaining the purpose of the study and ensuring confidentiality.

RESULTS:

FIGURE 2: POLL QUESTION: WHICH TYPES OF NOTIFICATIONS DO YOU RECEIVE MOST FREQUENTLY?

FIGURE 1: POLL QUESTION: HOW MANY NOTIFICATIONS DO YOU RECEIVE MOST FREQUENTLY?

FIGURE 3: POLL QUESTION: DO YOU HAVE NOTIFICATIONS TURNED ON FOR ALL APPS, OR DO YOU SELECTIVELY CHOOSE WHICH APPS CAN SEND NOTIFICATIONS?

ANALYSE:

Figure 1

Participants in the study were given the following choices when asked to estimate how many notifications they receive each day:

- A) Between 50 and 100 notifications: 65% of respondents agree with this option, suggesting that a sizable majority of students deal with a moderate amount of notification activity during the day. This implies that notifications are frequent enough to demand attention but not intrusive for a large number of students.
- B) From 100 to 500 notifications: This option was chosen by about 25% of participants, indicating that a significant percentage of students are exposed to a large frequency of alerts. This degree of involvement may cause disruptions and diversions from their study schedules, which could affect their focus and academic performance.
- C) According to the research, the majority of students receive between 50 and 100 notifications every day. While this may be tolerable, it is nevertheless big enough to interfere with their ability to focus when learning a language. Concerns regarding possible interruptions in their academic performance are raised by the fact that 25% of them receive between 100 and 500 notifications. Finally, it may be quite difficult for 11% who receive more than 500 notifications to stay focused on their studies.

Figure 2

The survey alternatives were presented to respondents in the study, which looked into the most common notification kinds that students receive:

- A) Social media alerts: 47% of participants chose this option, suggesting that social media platforms account for half of the notifications that students receive. This high percentage indicates that students are actively using social media and give

- priority to updates from friends, groups, and trending content, demonstrating the important role that social media plays in their everyday lives.
- B) App notifications: A significant percentage of students receive frequent notifications from a variety of programs as evidenced by the 34% of them who chose this choice. The different ways students engage with technology outside social media is demonstrated by these notifications, which could include updates from news apps, productivity tools, or entertainment platforms.
- C) Texts: Only 19% of participants selected this, showing that text message notifications are the least common among the three categories. This lower percentage may suggest a shift in communication preferences among students, as they increasingly favor instant messaging apps and social media for their interactions over traditional SMS.

Figure 3

The following conclusions can be drawn from the survey's findings about turning on or off notifications according to which ways:

- A) Selectively: There are 67% of students in this choice and they would rather selectively enable notifications from particular apps. This suggests that students are aware of their digital environments and seek to reduce distractions by allowing notifications from only those apps that they consider relevant or important.
- B) For none: 18% of students have opted out of notifications entirely. This choice may reflect a desire for a more focused and distraction-free experience, allowing them to engage with their devices on their own terms without interruptions from various applications.
- C) For all apps: Just 15% of respondents selected this option, recommending that some students do not permit notifications from all apps. This might show a desire to remain current on all platforms, but it could also result in information overload and other diversions.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

The first figure results emphasize the need for appropriate smartphone notification management techniques, particularly in educational settings where the focus is essential for excellent learning outcomes. The next figure's findings show how student communication is changing, with social media and app-based interactions taking precedence over text messaging. Teachers and developers can construct more effective communication tactics and tools that are suited to the tastes and habits of their pupils by having a better understanding of these trends. The insights in the third figure highlight how crucial customized notification settings are

to raising students' level of productivity and general digital well-being. By being aware of these performances, educators and app developers may design more effective resources and learning environments that meet the needs of their students. According to the research, most students (67%) prefer to selectively regulate their app notifications, indicating a deliberate attempt to stay focused and in charge of their online activities. Just 15% of respondents permit notifications from all apps, while a smaller percentage (18%) decide to completely disable notifications. These findings highlight how crucial customized notification settings are to raising students' level of productivity and general digital well-being. By being aware of these preferences, educators and app developers may design more effective resources and learning environments that meet the needs of their students.

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